

A Note on the Vanadates of Heavy Metals.

BY M. B. RANE and K. KONDIAH.

Of the earlier investigations on the vanadates of metals, the pioneer work of Roscoe (*Phil. Trans.*, 1870, 160, 317), Manasse (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1886, 773) and of Ditte (*Compt. rend.*, 1887, 104, 1705) may be mentioned. Recently Ephraim and Beck (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1926, 9, 38) prepared the vanadates of Ni, Co, Cu, Be, Zn, Mn, etc., by the double decomposition of the corresponding metallic sulphates by barium acid vanadate, which thus gave rise to complex salts, having the general formula $2MO, 3V_2O_5, 12$ or $15H_2O$ and less frequently $3MO, 5V_2O_5, nH_2O$. In the present investigation, the isolation, preparation and composition of vanadates of Hg, Au, Th, Ce and Zr are described.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The starting materials used in the preparation of the vanadate are ammonium *meta*-vanadate, obtained by careful crystallisation from an ammoniacal solution of V_2O_5 and potassium *pyro*-vanadate, obtained by fusion of two molecules of K_2CO_3 with one molecule of V_2O_5 in a platinum crucible, which was subsequently lixiviated with water and crystallised and washed free from carbonate. All the chemicals used were Merck's extra pure materials.

Carnot (*Compt. rend.*, 1887, 105, 119) obtained an orange coloured substance by the action of mercurous nitrate on a soluble vanadate. Treadwell (*Qualitative Analysis*, 1927, p. 545) however, describes mercurous vanadate as white in neutral solution. In the present investigation, the same orange-coloured compound was obtained by the action of mercurous nitrate with ammonium vanadate. On analysis, the composition of the compound has been found to be the same as given by Carnot (*loc. cit.*). With a large excess of ammonium vanadate however, the colour of the compound is almost dark brown to black containing excess of V_2O_5 . This is probably due to the presence of metallic mercury in a very fine

state, resulting from the partial decomposition of the mercurous vanadate.

Mercuric Vanadate.—Carnot (*loc. cit.*) failed to obtain any precipitate with HgCl_2 and alkali vanadate in the acid solution, but obtained a white and pale yellow precipitate in neutral and alkaline solutions respectively. In the present investigation, although no precipitate was obtained even on boiling the mixture of ammonium vanadate and mercuric chloride, a golden yellow precipitate was readily thrown down on addition of alcohol. The precipitate was, however, found to pass into the colloidal state on washing with water. The same precipitate was easily obtained by using alcoholic solution of mercuric chloride. The precipitate, though amorphous at first, soon becomes granular and when observed under a microscope appears crystalline, having a yellow colour in the transmitted light and a greenish tinge in reflected light. The preparation of this compound, however offers no difficulty if the nitrate of mercury is used instead of the chloride. The mercuric vanadate is found to be soluble in mineral acids, but not in acetic acid. It is also soluble in alkali chloride but not so in the nitrate. This explains the reason why Carnot failed to obtain the precipitate of the vanadate with mercuric chloride, and why it is so readily obtained with the nitrate. The alkali chloride peptises the precipitate, which thereby passes into the colloidal state. On heating, mercuric vanadate darkens in colour and finally decomposes at about 250° , mercury volatilising and V_2O_5 remaining behind. In order to determine the composition of the dried compound, mercury was determined as sulphide and vanadium estimated volumetrically in the filtrate. (Found: V_2O_5 , 29.74; HgO , 70.34. 2HgO , V_2O_5 requires V_2O_5 , 29.77; HgO , 70.23 per cent.). Thus mercuric vanadate has the composition 2HgO , V_2O_5 .

Mercury ortho-Vanadate.—A thick orange precipitate is obtained by the addition of excess of cold solution of potassium ortho-vanadate to mercuric nitrate. This compound is also soluble in alkali chlorides and mineral acids. On heating, this compound behaves like the *meta* compound. On analysis of the dried sample, its composition is found to approximate to the formula 3HgO , V_2O_5 . (Found: V_2O_5 , 22.95; HgO (by difference), 77.05. 3HgO , V_2O_5 requires V_2O_5 , 21.9; HgO , 78.1 per cent.).

Gold Vanadate.—Hundeshagen (*Chem. Zeit.*, 1905, 29, 799) failed to obtain any precipitate by the action of vanadic acid or

vanadic compounds with solutions of gold. The present authors find that although no precipitate is obtained by the action of solutions of ammonium vanadate and gold chloride even on heating, the colour of the resulting solution deepens. A golden yellow precipitate is however thrown down in presence of alcohol or electrolytes like ammonium chloride, indicating thereby the colloidal nature of the compound formed before precipitation. The yellow compound is unstable and the colour changes on standing to black. On washing, the freshly prepared precipitate passes into the colloidal state carrying a negative charge as shown by cataphoresis. On heating in a closed tube, the dry precipitate darkens in colour, gives out ammonia and finally decomposes into gold and V_2O_5 . A dried sample of the neutral freshly prepared compound gave on analysis the following results. (Found: Au_2O_3 , 51.62; V_2O_5 , 42.19; $(NH_4)_2O$ (by difference), 6.19. Au_2O_3 , $(NH_4)_2O$, $2V_2O_5$ requires Au_2O_3 , 51.55; V_2O_5 , 42.39; $(NH_4)_2O$, 6.06 per cent.).

With potassium *ortho*-vanadate and gold chloride, however, a hydrated compound having the composition Au_2O_3 , $2V_2O_5$, H_2O is obtained. (Found: Au_2O_3 , 53.21; V_2O_5 , 44.22; H_2O (by difference) 2.57. Au_2O_3 , $2V_2O_5$, H_2O requires Au_2O_3 , 53.67; V_2O_5 , 44.16; H_2O , 2.27 per cent.).

Thorium Vanadate.—By the action of a solution of ammonium-*meta*-vanadate on a dilute solution of thorium chloride, Volck (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1894, 6, 161) obtained a greenish yellow precipitate, which according to him on drying had the composition ThO_2 , V_2O_5 , $6H_2O$. The present authors obtained with thorium nitrate and ammonium *meta*-vanadate, a yellow compound that fades in colour on standing and on heating turns into a green mass, insoluble in dilute mineral acids. By treating with strong acids, V_2O_5 passes gradually into green solution and ThO_2 remains behind. With thorium chloride however, a heavy bright coloured substance is obtained, which does not lose colour on standing. The dried sample on analysis is found to approximate to the composition ThO_2 , V_2O_5 , H_2O . (Found: V_2O_5 , 40.33; ThO_2 , 56.74; H_2O (by difference), 2.93. ThO_2 , V_2O_5 , H_2O requires V_2O_5 , 39.21; ThO_2 , 56.92; H_2O , 3.87 per cent.).

Cerium Vanadate.—With ceric nitrate and excess of ammonium vanadate, a yellowish white precipitate is obtained. This rapidly changes to dark brown. With excess of ceric nitrate, no darkening

takes place. On using a saturated solution of ceric sulphate, however, a beautiful light yellow precipitate is thrown down, which settles readily. The compound is crystalline and on heating in a closed tube, it loses water and decomposes leaving behind a mixture of CeO_2 and V_2O_5 . The analysis of a dried sample shows the composition to be $3\text{CeO}_2, \text{V}_2\text{O}_5, 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (Found : CeO_2 , 59.90 ; V_2O_5 , 21.15 ; H_2O (by difference), 18.95. $3\text{CeO}_2, \text{V}_2\text{O}_5, 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires CeO_2 , 60.17 ; V_2O_5 , 21.08 ; H_2O , 18.75 per cent.).

Zirconium Vanadate.—A thick gelatinous yellow precipitate is obtained on treating a solution of zirconium nitrate with excess of ammonium vanadate. This is soluble in mineral acids and the dried sample on ignition in a closed tube loses water and finally decomposes into ZrO_2 and V_2O_5 .

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY,
BENARES.

Received February 23, 1931.